

Imaging exams from a European cohort of Diffuse Intrinsic Pontine Glioma (DIPG) patients. In a subcohort of patients, the annotation of the primary tumor, manually delineated by experienced radiologists is included.

ID: 4087a5c0-a43c-4766-aed4-dead740905a4

URL: <https://eucaim-node.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/4087a5c0-a43c-4766-aed4-dead740905a4/details>

Creation date: 2025-01-31 10:32:02.623634+00:00

License: EUCAIM Terms and Conditions [https://dashboard.eucaim.cancerimage.eu/eucaim_usage_policy.pdf]

Contact info.: info.primage@i3m.upv.es

Studies count: 161

Subjects count: 65

Age range: Between 2 years and 17 years

Sex: Female, Male, Undifferentiated, Unkown

Body part(s): HEAD, BRAIN, LSPINE, SPINE, SKULL, OPTIC CANAL, CSPINE, Unknown

Modality: MR, CT, OT